

THE ROLE OF BLOOM TAXONOMY IN DEVELOPING PRAGMATIC COMPETENCE IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: Ushbu maqolada xorijiy tilni o'rganishda pragmatic kompetensiyani rivojlantirishning ahamiyati va Blum taksonomiyasi haqidagi ilmiy fikrlar atroflicha muhokama qilindi. Blum taksonomiyasi va mazkur taksonomiyaning Lorin Anderson va David Kraswall tomonidan taklif qilingan o'zgarishlari xorijiy tillarni o'rganishda ham muhim ahamiyatga ega hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: taksonomiya, Blum, pragmatika, kommunikativ, kompetensiya, til o'rganish, til o'rgatish, nutq, qobiliyat, nutqiy aktlar.

Abstract: In this article, the importance of developing pragmatic competence in learning a foreign language and scientific opinions about Bloom's taxonomy were discussed in detail. Bloom's taxonomy and its modifications proposed by Lorin Anderson and David Kraswall are also important in foreign language learning.

Key words: taxonomy, Bloom, pragmatics, communicative, competence, language learning, language teaching, speech, ability, speech acts.

Абстракт: В данной статье подробно рассмотрены важность развития прагматической компетентности при изучении иностранного языка и научные мнения о таксономии Блума. Таксономия Блума и ее модификации, предложенные Лорином Андерсоном и Дэвидом Красволлом, также важны для изучения иностранных языков.

Ключевые слова: таксономия, Блума, прагматика, коммуникативность, компетентность, изучение языка, обучение языку, речь, способности, речевые акты.

Introduction

Learning a foreign language means acquiring the language in all spheres which requires from a teacher great responsibility. According to the state education standard for foreign languages of the continuing education system, foreign language communicative competence is the ability to use the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities in the process of communication. In this standard, communicative competence includes the following types: **Linguistic competence**, i.e., knowledge of phonetics, lexicon, grammar, and speech activities, implies the acquisition of skills in listening, speaking, reading, and writing. **Sociolinguistic competence** makes it possible to choose the necessary linguistic form and expression method based on a speech situation, communicative goal and desire of the speaker. Sociolinguistic competence includes socio-cultural competence and the ability to present the national characteristics of authentic speech by knowing the customs, values, rituals and other national-cultural characteristics of the country where one lives and comparing it with the country where the language is organized. **Pragmatic competence** refers to the ability to get out of difficult situations by repeatedly asking, apologizing, etc. In this standard, discourse competence is included in pragmatic competence. This competence implies the expression of thoughts in oral or written speech using appropriate language tools. Discourse competence refers to the ability to understand and interpret linguistic signals to ensure coherence in oral or written speech.

In order to achieve all spheres of this communicative competence we would like to use taxonomy, that is renewed Bloom taxonomy in English lesson. The system of questions and tasks founded by the famous American psychologist and pedagogue Benjamin Blum - the taxonomy of educational goals based on the levels of cognitive activity is quite common in the world of modern education. Taxonomy of educational goals is the categorization or systematization of concrete actions of students indicating

a certain level of mastery, content objects, which become more complex based on natural interdependence. Taxonomy is a theory of classification and systematization of complex structured areas of existence.

Literature review and methods

While pragmatics has played an important role in first and second language classroom research, classroom research has played only a minor role in foreign language pragmatics. As an example, early observation schedules included the following speech act categories for examining teachers' conversations: accept, discuss, mention, praise, confirm, joke, clarify, summarize, repeat, question, inform, lecture, correct, give instructions, request, criticize included. Perhaps the best-known scheme for analyzing classroom discourse is the hierarchical structure model. Although pragmatics thus occupies an important position as a research tool, little attention has been paid to pragmatics as a subject of classroom research. One of the central questions in second language acquisition research is how instruction affects second language development, yet a comprehensive review of research on this topic finds conspicuously few reports on the effects of instruction on learners' acquisition of L2 pragmatics.

However, Benjamin Bloom's classic learning taxonomy, published in 1956 was revised and refined by Lorin Anderson and David Kraswall in 2000.

Understanding	the learner's ability to comprehend information
Apply	the learner's ability to use information in new ways
Analyze	learner's ability to break down information into its essential parts
Evaluate	learner's ability to judge and critique information
Create/Design	the learner's ability to create something new from different elements of information

By categorizing levels of cognitive ability, Bloom's taxonomy for English language instruction can help you set clear classroom goals, discover appropriate approaches to different types of lessons, and select the best way to measure learners' progress in language skills. When a teacher gives a learner the task of inferring meaning from a sentence that contains a significant number of nouns, verbs, adjectives, and discourse signs that are unfamiliar to the learner. The task would require them to analyze how each word is related syntactically and semantically. The three higher levels of thinking coexist in the same "unsophisticated" task of reading comprehension. However, it is doubtful that the average curriculum planner or non-linguistic observer would recognize that the task "hits" the highest level of Bloom's taxonomy.

Results

This leads to the biggest problem with Bloom's Taxonomy when it is used in educational settings: misinterpretation or failure to understand the nature of language learning and the cognitive mechanisms that regulate it at different developmental levels. Being creative in modern foreign languages, at lower levels of proficiency, is less about producing content, tasks, and artifacts than it is about making hypotheses about how the target language works, taking risks (creatively seeking opportunities to test those hypotheses), and coming up with communication strategies (creatively compensating for lack of knowledge of foreign language vocabulary), and figuring out better ways to learn on their own (creatively applying metacognitive strategies) are relevant.

Discussions

Another important issue concerns the way humans process language in comprehending and producing foreign words. The brain gradually automates the cognitive skills contained in the three categories that Bloom's Taxonomy places at the bottom of the pyramid.

Furthermore, a very important issue is that many teachers feel pressure to work on the higher levels of Bloom's Taxonomy as often as possible, since the nature of L2 acquisition is cumulative and the jump from one level to the next must be justified by

the learner's readiness to deal with the cognitive and linguistic demands that level places on the learner's procedural skills. Once one level is mastered, one can move on to the next level, and each level provides a scaffold (in Vygotsky's terms) for the level immediately above. If the teacher feels that the learner is still "stuck" at a level that requires more extensive practice, the class should stay at that level, and it is ethically wrong to move to a higher level simply to reach the top level of Bloom's Taxonomy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, acquiring pragmatic competence in L2 has important role in building communicative competent of a learner, both in productive and receptive speech. It means that English language learner could understand the language forms and functions that are appropriate. For this, Benjamin Bloom's model, especially in the adaptation by Anderson et al. should be used as what it was intended to be, a comprehensive classification of the various goals educators should set for students across the cognitive, affective, and motor domains of learning It should be. Bloom's taxonomy was intended to help curriculum designers and teachers not lose sight of the scope and primary goals of effective learning.

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